

Artifact Evaluation Instruction for Testbench analysis using non-invasive fault injection

What is the part that can be evaluated?

Results presented in the paper

The paper presents and demonstrates methodology used for validating testbench capability of finding errors in digital designs during simulation. The results presented that can be validated is first of all that the supplied code, shown in the paper section IV “Usage examples”, will generate the same output as indicated in the paper.

This means that the waveform in Figure 5, “Simulation waveform” can be replicated with both the VHDL and the Python based testbenches along with the DUT code. Furthermore, the VHDL test shall yield the same text result as shown in Listing 6 “Console log from VHDL test without using queue”, and the Python testbench shall give the same text result as shown in Listing 9. “Console log for the python testbench implemented with queue parsing”.

Methodology concept

The testbench mentioned in section II B “Motivation” is provided along with a simulation module that has errors according to the test. This testbench uses the methodology mentioned in the paper and shall report tests performed and whether FIAT-tests or ordinary tests were successful. Ordinary tests shall return a list of errors found during compilation, but the list length will vary due to the use of randomized data. The ordinary tests shall run until the end, even though errors are reported.

The main motivation for providing this example is that it is a real-world example using the presented methodology. In addition, fellow researchers and teachers in the field can play with the test setup, to see how different types of errors are reported. Technically the options to manipulate the testbench or the simulation code are endless, but proving the concept can be shown with less effort. In the paper, our claim is that using the FIAT-methodology yields higher confidence in functional testing. The easiest way to show this is that the FIAT-tests will yield reports of faulty testing when we skip ordinary checks (as if they did not do what they should) to make the ordinary verification pass its tests.

The validation for this part is thus that the testbench does run and will provide results for the ordinary tests regardless of the outcome of the FIAT-tests. Furthermore, bypassing ordinary checks during testing shall lead to failure report on the FIAT-tests, which reminds us to fix the underlying issue, as intended.

Evaluation Checklist

The checklist is included at the end of this document.

The entire process described may be completed within an hour, including installation.

Required and provided software

OS

For this evaluation, a linux based system is required. Our tests were performed in windows subsystem for linux (WSL), combined with an aptainer running fedora linux.

Text editor

To view and modify code, a text editor is required. There are no particular version requirements for text editors, but it is preferable to be able to display line numbers, such as anyone suited for programming notepad++, vscode, emacs, etc.

Waveform viewer

To evaluate waveform output some sort of .vcd waveform viewer is required. The requirements for the viewer software is not strict, but we have provided the installation instructions for gtkwave which is an open source tool for this purpose. There are also online tools, that can be used for this purpose. <https://vc.drom.io> has shown to provide the required output for this evaluation (24.March 2025), although it has limited capacity compared to installed tools.

The waveform viewer is separated from the aptainer, because we cannot guarantee that the aptainer will provide a GUI using different base systems.

Verification software Aptainer

The testbenches can be run with different types of EDA software along with the cocotb-framework.

Modifications may be required when depending on tools and versions in use. In order to avoid this becoming a problem, we have thus provided a container file of the “aptainer” type, providing

- Fedora Linux
- GHDL 5.0.1
 - For VHDL simulation
- Python 3.13
 - For running python based testbenches
- Numpy 2.2.4
 - To support fixed integer bit widths
- Cocotb 1.9.2
 - For cosimulation using GHDL and Python together
- Git 2.49.0
 - For downloading git-repositories (not required at this point)

While each of these can be installed individually, installing the aptainer environment and using the provided .sif file, reduces the installations required for running tests to one.

Installation instructions

Apptainer environment

Apptainer is similar to docker. According to their documentation most dockers can be run using their framework.

A full installation guide for apptainer can be found here

<https://apptainer.org/docs/admin/main/installation.html#>

For a Debian/ubuntu linux system, such as Windows subsystem for Linux (WSL), the following instructions should be sufficient. *For other operating systems(OS'es), please refer to the apptainer.org installation guide.*

```
curl -fsSL https://nvidia.github.io/libnvidia-container/gpgkey | sudo gpg --dearmor -o /usr/share/keyrings/nvidia-container-toolkit-keyring.gpg \  
curl -s -L https://nvidia.github.io/libnvidia-container/stable/deb/nvidia-container-toolkit.list | \  
sed 's#deb https://#deb [signed-by=/usr/share/keyrings/nvidia-container-toolkit-keyring.gpg] https://#g' | \  
sudo tee /etc/apt/sources.list.d/nvidia-container-toolkit.list \  
sudo apt-get update  
sudo apt-get install -y nvidia-container-toolkit  
  
sudo apt update  
sudo apt install -y software-properties-common  
  
sudo add-apt-repository -y ppa:apptainer/ppa  
sudo apt update  
sudo apt install -y apptainer
```

Note: If it is difficult to read or copy from this textbox, you will find the instructions in the readme.txt file.

GTKWave, waveform viewer

To install gtkwave on a Debian/linux system a package manager can be used:

```
sudo apt install gtkwave # for Debian, Ubuntu
```

For other OS'es, please refer to the GTKWave documentation:

https://gtkwave.github.io/gtkwave/install/unix_linux.html#compiling-and-installing

Note: Since other vcd viewers can be used, this step may be omitted.

Files

- Create a folder for the evaluation project.
- Unzip the FIAT.zip file to this folder.

Evaluation Instructions

Start the apptainer from the folder containing the fiat-apptainer.sif:

```
apptainer shell ./fiat-apptainer.sif
```

Evaluate the usage-example VHDL testbench

VHDL testbench text output evaluation

Move to the folder containing the VHDL testbench and run the testbench script

```
Apptainer> cd usage-examples/src/
```

```
Apptainer> ./run.sh
```

This should give the following text output, equivalent to that of Listing 6 in the paper:

```
Apptainer> ./run.sh
../../src/ieee2008/numeric_std-body.vhdl:1873:7:@0ms:(assertion warning): NUMERIC_STD."=": metavalue detected, returning FALSE
../../src/ieee2008/numeric_std-body.vhdl:3036:7:@5ns:(assertion warning): NUMERIC_STD.TO_INTEGER: metavalue detected, returning 0
../../src/ieee2008/numeric_std-body.vhdl:3036:7:@10ns:(assertion warning): NUMERIC_STD.TO_INTEGER: metavalue detected, returning 0
tb_FIAT_min.vhdl:48:7:@50ns:(assertion error): count (5) != behavioral model: (2)
tb_FIAT_min.vhdl:51:7:@50ns:(assertion error): count (5) > 4, ** Maximum value exceeded
tb_FIAT_min.vhdl:48:7:@120ns:(assertion error): count (6) != behavioral model: (3)
tb_FIAT_min.vhdl:51:7:@120ns:(assertion error): count (6) > 4, ** Maximum value exceeded
tb_FIAT_min.vhdl:48:7:@125ns:(assertion error): count (7) != behavioral model: (4)
tb_FIAT_min.vhdl:51:7:@125ns:(assertion error): count (7) > 4, ** Maximum value exceeded
tb_FIAT_min.vhdl:48:7:@130ns:(assertion error): count (7) != behavioral model: (4)
tb_FIAT_min.vhdl:51:7:@130ns:(assertion error): count (7) > 4, ** Maximum value exceeded
simulation stopped @185ns
Apptainer> █
```

```
run -all
## Warning: NUMERIC_STD."=": metavalue detected,
returning FALSE
# Time: 0 ns Iteration: 0 Instance: /tb_fiat/DUT
## Warning: NUMERIC_STD.TO_INTEGER: metavalue
detected, returning 0
# Time: 5 ns Iteration: 0 Instance: /tb_fiat
## Error: count (5) != behavioral model: (2)
# Time: 50 ns Iteration: 0 Instance: /tb_fiat
## Error: count (5) > 4, ** Maximum value exceeded
# Time: 50 ns Iteration: 0 Instance: /tb_fiat
## Error: count (6) != behavioral model: (3)
# Time: 120 ns Iteration: 0 Instance: /tb_fiat
## Error: count (6) > 4, ** Maximum value exceeded
# Time: 120 ns Iteration: 0 Instance: /tb_fiat
## Error: count (7) != behavioral model: (4)
# Time: 125 ns Iteration: 0 Instance: /tb_fiat
## Error: count (7) > 4, ** Maximum value exceeded
# Time: 125 ns Iteration: 0 Instance: /tb_fiat
## Error: count (7) != behavioral model: (4)
# Time: 130 ns Iteration: 0 Instance: /tb_fiat
## Error: count (7) > 4, ** Maximum value exceeded
# Time: 130 ns Iteration: 0 Instance: /tb_fiat
```

Text Copy from Listing 6 in the paper

Looking at the text output, every inserted error is found at the exact same time as in the example from the paper. The difference in reporting is only the textual output provided by Questa (from the article) and GHDL5.0.1 (Apptainer).

Explanation: All these error-reports were generated from two errors injected. The first was injected on the falling clock edge, when the count has reached 2, while the second was injected after resetting and counting to three. The difference in persistence is caused by the first error to be generated by overriding outputs only (blackbox FIAT-method), while the second was generated by altering the DUT internal state, causing errors every halfcycle until reset.

VHDL testbench Waveform evaluation

This run has created a vcd waveform “wave.vcd”. This can be opened (outside the aptainer).

```
Apptainer> exit
cd usage-examples/src
gtkwave wave.vcd
```

This will open the GTKWave viewer with the waveform loaded.

To view the waveform, the signals must be selected and everything must be zoomed out:

- In the upper left “SST” subwindow, select the “tb_fiat”

- This will display the signals in the subwindow below
- In the subwindow below “SST”, drag and drop the four signals to the “signals” subwindow
- In the “SST” window expand the “tb_fiat” and select “dut”
- In the subwindow below “SST” drag and drop “r_count” to the “signals” subwindow
- Arrange the signals in the “signals” subwindow to taste
- Press the “Zoom fit” button (or use the menu Time->Zoom->Zoom best fit)

The view should be something like this:

This should give a comparable view to the article Fig.5.

The window may need to be stretched slightly (+ reapply zoom fit) to show the binary output values in the waveform.

Copy of fig.5 From the article

The initial difference is only that simulation model of a quinary counter, tqcount is added compared to the article figure.

Explanation: What we see is that the output value (count) is forced to become b101 after 45 ns, and released after reaching 50ns. This does not affect the internal register value, but reported by the testbench after 50 ns. The next fault injection happens at 115 ns where the register value is forced to b110, causing errors to be detected at 120, 125 and 130 ns. The system is reset at 130 ns.

VHDL testbench code evaluation

The VHDL testbench “tb_FIAT_min.vhdl” and the dut “Qcount.vhdl” can be further inspected, to validate that the code is the same as given in the paper listing1-5.

The “run.sh” script is only there to start the simulation using GHDL.

Evaluate the usage-example python test bench

Python testbench text output evaluation

The method for evaluating the python testbench will be similar to the VHDL testbench:

Move to the folder with the fiat-apptainer.sif file, start the apptainer and browse to the python testbench folder.

The python testbench will use the same dut-file (Qcount.vhdl) but it is started from the usage-examples/test/ folder:

```

apptainer shell ./fiat-apptainer.sif
Apptainer> cd usage-examples/test/
Apptainer> make

```

The full text output should be something like this:

```

Apptainer> make
rm -f results.xml
"make" -f makefile results.xml
make[1]: Entering directory '/home/yngveha/Yngve/apptainer/usage-examples/test'
mkdir -p sim_build
\
/usr/local/sbin/ghdl -i --std=08 --workdir=sim_build --work=work /home/yngveha/Yngve/apptainer/usage-examples/test/./src/*.vhd* && \
/usr/local/sbin/ghdl -m --std=08 --workdir=sim_build -Psim_build --work=work qcount --vpi=/usr/local/lib64/python3.13/s
rm -f results.xml
MODULE=tb_FIAT_min TESTCASE= TOPLEVEL=qcount TOPLEVEL_LANG=vhdl \
/usr/local/sbin/ghdl -r --std=08 --time-resolution=ps --workdir=sim_build -Psim_build --work=work qcount --vpi=/usr/local/lib64/python3.13/s
ite-packages/cocotb/libs/libcocotbvpi_ghdl.so --vcd=qcount.vcd
loading VPI module '/usr/local/lib64/python3.13/site-packages/cocotb/libs/libcocotbvpi_ghdl.so'
  --ns INFO      gpi                .mbed/gpi_embed.cpp:79  in set_program_name_in_venv      Did not detect Python vir
tual environment. Using system-wide Python interpreter
  --ns INFO      gpi                ../gpi/GpiCommon.cpp:101 in gpi_print_registered_impl    VPI registered
VPI module loaded!
  0.00ns INFO    cocotb                Running on GHDL version 5.0.1 (tarball) [Dunoon edition]
  0.00ns INFO    cocotb                Running tests with cocotb v1.9.2 from /usr/local/lib64/python3.13/site-packages/cocotb
  0.00ns INFO    cocotb                Seeding Python random module with 1743004032
  0.00ns INFO    cocotb.regression      pytest not found, install it to enable better AssertionError messages
  0.00ns INFO    cocotb.regression      Found test tb_FIAT_min.main_test
  0.00ns INFO    cocotb.regression      running main_test (1/1)
././src/ieee2008/numeric_std-body.vhdl:1873:7:@0ms: (assertion warning): NUMERIC_STD."=": metavalue detected, returning FALSE
  60.00ns INFO    cocotb.qcount          FIAT OK: Max error found @ 45.0ns, count=5, behavioral model = 2
  130.00ns INFO   cocotb.qcount          FIAT OK: Max error found @ 115.0ns, count=6, behavioral model = 3
  185.00ns INFO   cocotb.regression      main_test passed
  185.00ns INFO   cocotb.regression
*****
** TEST                STATUS SIM TIME (ns) REAL TIME (s) RATIO (ns/s) **
*****
** tb_FIAT_min.main_test  PASS           185.00           0.00    42552.81 **
*****
** TESTS=1 PASS=1 FAIL=0 SKIP=0           185.00           0.01    22844.92 **
*****

make[1]: Leaving directory '/home/yngveha/Yngve/apptainer/usage-examples/test'
Apptainer> █

```

This can be compared to the text output from listing 9 in the article:

```

run -all
# ** Warning: NUMERIC_STD."=": metavalue detected, returning FALSE
# Time: 0 ns Iteration: 0 Instance: /qcount
# 60.00ns INFO cocotb.qcount FIAT OK: Max error found @ 45.0ns, count=5, behavioral model = 2
# 130.00ns INFO cocotb.qcount FIAT OK: Max error found @ 115.0ns, count=6, behavioral model = 3
# 186.00ns INFO cocotb.regression main_test passed
Copy of Listing 9. Console log for the python testbench implemented with queue parsing.

```

The part to look for is what is reported at 60ns and 130ns. This should be the same as with Questa. The fact that the Questa report ends at 186 ns compared to 185ns with GHDL is probably a feature in how cocotb and Questa communicates or report simulation end, and it is insignificant in this context.

Explanation: The python based testbench does the same fault injections as the VHDL-test, but it stores all error messages in a queue, which is checked for each fault injection. If the injected fault is detected, success is reported.

Python testbench waveform evaluation

The python testbench waveform “qcount.vcd” is created in the test folder where the python testbench resides. As with the previous vcd file, it must be viewed outside the apptainer.

```

Apptainer> exit

cd usage-examples/test

gtkwave qcount.vcd

```

When using gtkwave, follow the same routine as with the VHDL testbench waveform.

An alternative method to view a simple vcd file like this is to drop it into an online vcd viewer. Here a screenshot from <https://vc.drom.io>

Output from gtkwave, after selecting the qcount signals, and stretching the window and zooming in fully:

Explanation: The difference to the VHDL testbench is that there is no layer for the testbench, so we do not get the testbench model result, only the DUT (Qcount) signals and ports. We can see that changing the output does not change the register or register input values (next_count, r_count), while changing the register value affects all subsequent values until reset is performed. The reset applied after the falling edge of the clock is a difference to the waveform, but this is not significant as it is read synchronously at the clock rising edges at 80 and 140 ns. The falling edge assertion is caused by awaiting ReadOnly() and then ReadWrite(), which is unnecessary but how it was written.

Apart from the reset being shorter, the waveform should be equivalent to the Fig.5 in the paper:

Copy of fig.5 From the article

Python testbench code evaluation

The Python testbench “tb_FIAT_min.vhdl” can be further inspected, to validate that the code is the same as given in the paper listing 7 and 8.

The “makefile” script is only there to start the simulation using cocotb and GHDL.

Evaluate the usecase.

Restart the fiat-apptainer.sif, and

```

apptainer shell ./fiat-apptainer.sif
Apptainer> cd usecase/test/
Apptainer> make

```

The text output will be slightly longer and different running this test.

Skipping the default text presenting the tools and files in use, we look at the testbench output text from the FIAT tests and the ordinary tests.

Fiat tests:

The FIAT tests is the main point in this context. When running the testbench we can observe the report that a number of tests have been performed and that they are found. The testbench will report each test and whether or not they have been found by the ordinary checkers. The number of FIAT-tests is fixed, and each injected error shall be found.

The interesting part for anyone reading the paper is to modify this part to see how we can manage when injected faults are not found during FIAT-testing.

```
0.00ns INFO cocotb Running on GHDL version 5.0.1 (tarball) [Dunoon edition]
0.00ns INFO cocotb Running tests with cocotb v1.9.2 from /usr/local/lib64/python3.13/site-packages/cocotb
0.00ns INFO cocotb Seeding Python random module with 1743008147
0.00ns INFO cocotb.regression pytest not found, install it to enable better AssertionError messages
0.00ns INFO cocotb.regression Found test tb_pwm.fiat_sequencer
0.00ns INFO cocotb.regression Found test tb_pwm.test_sequencer
0.00ns INFO cocotb.regression running fiat sequencer (1/2)
Starts monitoring tasks and stimuli generators
0.00ns INFO cocotb.pulse_width_modulator Starting clock
0.00ns INFO cocotb.pulse_width_modulator *** FAULT INJECTION RUNNING ***
0.00ns INFO cocotb.pulse_width_modulator Resetting module...
../../src/ieee2008/numeric_std-body.vhdl:3062:7:@0ms:(assertion warning): NUMERIC_STD.TO_INTEGER: metavalue detected, returning 0
0.00ns INFO cocotb.pulse_width_modulator Injecting error: Enable during reset...
1.00ns INFO cocotb.pulse_width_modulator Starting monitoring events
10.00ns INFO cocotb.pulse_width_modulator Completed: Reset test
20.00ns INFO cocotb.pulse_width_modulator Found error: Reset @ 10.0ns...
20.00ns INFO cocotb.pulse_width_modulator Injecting error: direction change during pulse...
20.00ns INFO cocotb.pulse_width_modulator Completed: Reset test
71.00ns INFO cocotb.pulse_width_modulator Found error: Short circuit @ 40.0ns...
71.00ns INFO cocotb.pulse_width_modulator Injecting error: pulse deassertion < 1 cycle before direction change
110.00ns INFO cocotb.pulse_width_modulator Found error: Short circuit @ 100.0ns...
110.00ns INFO cocotb.pulse_width_modulator Injecting error: pulse deassertion < 1 cycle after direction change
159.00ns INFO cocotb.pulse_width_modulator Found error: Short circuit @ 150.0ns...
159.00ns INFO cocotb.pulse_width_modulator Injecting error: Too late response on direction change
230.00ns INFO cocotb.pulse_width_modulator Found error: Direction @ 190.0ns...
230.00ns INFO cocotb.pulse_width_modulator Injecting error: Pulsing too fast
320.00ns INFO cocotb.pulse_width_modulator Found error: Duty cycle @ 280.0ns...
320.00ns INFO cocotb.pulse_width_modulator Injecting error: Setting one duty cycle and pulsing another
160550.00ns INFO cocotb.pulse_width_modulator Duty cycles: Set dc: -25.0%, Measured dc: -50.0%, period = 160.0us, f = 6.25kHz
320570.00ns INFO cocotb.pulse_width_modulator Found error: Duty cycle @ 160550.0ns...
320570.00ns INFO cocotb.pulse_width_modulator Injected faults managed!
320580.00ns INFO cocotb.pulse_width_modulator *** FAULT INJECTION COMPLETE ***
320580.00ns INFO cocotb.regression fiat sequencer passed
320580.00ns INFO cocotb.regression running test sequencer (2/2)
```

Ordinary tests:

The ordinary tests are designed to find a number of errors typical for a student delivery of a synthesizable pulse width modulation (PWM) design. The PWM design shall be used with a DC motor connected to an H-bridge to be run in different directions. The duty cycle input uses signed input to determine duty cycle and direction.

A PWM simulation module is provided. The simulation module does PWM at the correct duty cycle and direction. The simulation module does not handle reset or considerations such as not changing direction without turning off the output. Direction changes while pulsing will lead to a short-circuit condition for the H-bridge that switches slow compared to an FPGA. Reset that does not turn off the PWM signal shall be found. The tests are designed to find these error among several others. Since the ordinary test uses a number of random duty cycles, the number of found errors may vary.

The testbench is programmed to finish all stimuli before reporting. The traceback of the last error will be be displayed. Before the cocotb test report.

```
320580.00ns INFO cocotb.regression running test sequencer (2/2)
Starts monitoring tasks and stimuli generators
Starting clock
320580.00ns INFO cocotb.pulse_width_modulator *** STARTING ORDINARY TESTS ***
320580.00ns INFO cocotb.pulse_width_modulator Starting duty cycle tests
320580.00ns INFO cocotb.pulse_width_modulator Resetting module...
320581.00ns INFO cocotb.pulse_width_modulator Starting monitoring events
320595.00ns INFO cocotb.pulse_width_modulator Completed: Reset test
550000.00ns INFO cocotb.pulse_width_modulator Duty cycles: Set dc: 50.0%, Measured dc: 50.0%, period = 150.0us, f = 6.67kHz
700000.00ns INFO cocotb.pulse_width_modulator Duty cycles: Set dc: 50.0%, Measured dc: 50.0%, period = 150.0us, f = 6.67kHz
1000000.00ns INFO cocotb.pulse_width_modulator Duty cycles: Set dc: -50.0%, Measured dc: -50.0%, period = 150.0us, f = 6.67kHz
1000000.00ns INFO cocotb.pulse_width_modulator Fixed duty tests complete
1270703.12ns INFO cocotb.pulse_width_modulator Duty cycles: Set dc: -69.0%, Measured dc: -69.0%, period = 150.0us, f = 6.67kHz
1603515.62ns INFO cocotb.pulse_width_modulator Duty cycles: Set dc: -47.0%, Measured dc: -47.0%, period = 150.0us, f = 6.67kHz
1931640.62ns INFO cocotb.pulse_width_modulator Duty cycles: Set dc: -28.0%, Measured dc: -28.0%, period = 150.0us, f = 6.67kHz
2197656.25ns INFO cocotb.pulse_width_modulator Duty cycles: Set dc: 51.0%, Measured dc: 51.0%, period = 150.0us, f = 6.67kHz
2276656.25ns INFO cocotb.pulse_width_modulator Random duty tests 1/2 complete
2347656.25ns INFO cocotb.pulse_width_modulator Duty cycles: Set dc: 51.0%, Measured dc: 51.0%, period = 150.0us, f = 6.67kHz
2347656.25ns INFO cocotb.pulse_width_modulator Resetting module...
2347671.25ns INFO cocotb.pulse_width_modulator Reset between duties complete
2347671.25ns INFO cocotb.pulse_width_modulator Completed: Reset test
2673437.50ns INFO cocotb.pulse_width_modulator Duty cycles: Set dc: -34.0%, Measured dc: -34.0%, period = 150.0us, f = 6.67kHz
2903125.00ns INFO cocotb.pulse_width_modulator Duty cycles: Set dc: -81.0%, Measured dc: -81.0%, period = 150.0us, f = 6.67kHz
3250000.00ns INFO cocotb.pulse_width_modulator Duty cycles: Set dc: 50.0%, Measured dc: 50.0%, period = 150.0us, f = 6.67kHz
3400000.00ns INFO cocotb.pulse_width_modulator Duty cycles: Set dc: 50.0%, Measured dc: 50.0%, period = 150.0us, f = 6.67kHz
3444000.00ns INFO cocotb.pulse_width_modulator Random duty tests 2/2 complete
3444000.00ns INFO cocotb.pulse_width_modulator Error found: Short circuit @700000.0ns
HALF-BRIDGE SHORT CIRCUITED: en active when changing direction
3444000.00ns INFO cocotb.pulse_width_modulator Error found: Short circuit @1931640.625ns
HALF-BRIDGE SHORT CIRCUITED: en active when changing direction
3444000.00ns INFO cocotb.pulse_width_modulator Error found: Reset @2347671.25ns
PWM enable has not been deasserted during reset
3444000.00ns INFO cocotb.pulse_width_modulator Error found: Short circuit @2347671.25ns
HALF-BRIDGE SHORT CIRCUITED: en active when changing direction
3444000.00ns INFO cocotb.pulse_width_modulator Error found: Short circuit @2903125.0ns
HALF-BRIDGE SHORT CIRCUITED: en active when changing direction
3444000.00ns INFO cocotb.regression test sequencer failed
Traceback (most recent call last):
  File "/home/yngveha/Yngve/apptainer/usecase/test/tb_pwm.py", line 306, in test_sequencer
    messages.check_queue(dut)
    ~~~~~^~~~~
  File "/home/yngveha/Yngve/apptainer/usecase/test/tb_pwm.py", line 77, in check_queue
    raise msg[2] # Provide traceback for the last error reported
    ~~~~~^~~~~
  File "/home/yngveha/Yngve/apptainer/usecase/test/tb_pwm.py", line 152, in check_short_circuit
    assert self.dut.en.value == 0, "HALF-BRIDGE SHORT CIRCUITED: en active when changing direction"
    ~~~~~^~~~~
AssertionError: HALF-BRIDGE SHORT CIRCUITED: en active when changing direction
```

End report:

The end report is the summary of how the @cocotb tests went. Unless the testbench has been altered, the FIAT-sequence should pass, while the (ordinary) test_sequencer should fail.

If this report isn't shown, that means the test did not come to an end as it should.

```
3444000.00ns INFO cocotb.regression *****
** TEST STATUS SIM TIME (ns) REAL TIME (s) RATIO (ns/s) **
*****
** tb_pwm.fiat_sequencer PASS 320580.00 1.15 278732.08 **
** tb_pwm.test_sequencer FAIL 3123420.00 8.48 368460.30 **
*****
** TESTS=2 PASS=1 FAIL=1 SKIP=0 3444000.00 9.79 351783.41 **
*****

make[1]: Leaving directory '/home/yngveha/Yngve/apptainer/usecase/test'
Apptainer>
```

Concept Evaluation:

In the `/usecase/test/` folder, open the testbench `tb_pwm.py`

The testbench features separate stimuli and checks. The checks are started by the `run` method in the `Monitor` class.

We can emulate an incomplete or forgotten test, by not starting that particular check.

Comment the code that starts the two tests that is triggered in the ordinary tests (line 131 and 132) in the `tb_pwm.py`, and save the test.

```
async def run(self):
    ''' start all checks '''
    await Timer(1, 'ns') # Settle uninitialized values
    self.dut._log.info("Starting monitoring events")
    self.en_mon = SignalEventMonitor(self.dut.en)
    self.duty_mon = SignalEventMonitor(self.dut.duty_cycle)
    self.reset_mon = SignalEventMonitor(self.dut.reset)
    #start_soon(self.check_reset())
    #start_soon(self.check_short_circuit())
    start_soon(self.check_timeout())
    start_soon(self.check_direction())
    start_soon(self.check_duty_cycle())
```

Run the testbench from the aptainer

```
aptainer shell ./fiat-aptainer.sif
Apptainer> cd usecase/test/
Apptainer> make
```

Evaluation:

When running the testbench, the FIAT tests shall now trigger, which stops the FIAT-tests, while the ordinary tests may complete successfully.

We will also get a warning for each remaining FIAT checks are not awaited, since the testbench does not use report management for FIAT test errors, and thus ends at the first error in a list already created.

```

0.00ns INFO cocotb.regression Found test tb_pwm.fiat_sequencer
0.00ns INFO cocotb.regression Found test tb_pwm.test_sequencer
0.00ns INFO cocotb.regression running fiat sequencer (1/2)
Starts monitoring tasks and stimuli generators
Starting clock
*** FAULT INJECTION RUNNING ***
Resetting module...
.../src/ieee2008/numeric_std-body.vhdl:3062:7:@0ms:(assertion warning): NUMERIC_STD.TO_INTEGER: metavalue detected, returning 0
0.00ns INFO cocotb.pulse_width_modulator Injecting error: Enable during reset...
0.00ns INFO cocotb.pulse_width_modulator Starting monitoring events
1.00ns INFO cocotb.pulse_width_modulator fiat sequencer failed
20.00ns INFO cocotb.regression
Traceback (most recent call last):
  File "/home/yngveha/Yngve/apptainer/usecase/test/tb_pwm.py", line 294, in fiat_sequen
    await fiat.run()
  File "/home/yngveha/Yngve/apptainer/usecase/test/tb_pwm.py", line 338, in run
    self.messages.find_error(self.dut, each[1])
FileNotFoundError: [Errno 2] No such file or directory: '...'
File "/home/yngveha/Yngve/apptainer/usecase/test/tb_pwm.py", line 82, in find_error
    raise AssertionError("NO_QUEUE")
AssertionError: NO_QUEUE
20.00ns INFO cocotb.regression running test sequencer (2/2)
Starts monitoring tasks and stimuli generators
Starting clock
*** STARTING ORDINARY TESTS ***
Starting duty cycle tests
Resetting module...
Starting monitoring events
Duty cycles: Set dc: 50.0%, Measured dc: 50.0%, period = 150.0us, f = 6.67kHz
Duty cycles: Set dc: 50.0%, Measured dc: 50.0%, period = 150.0us, f = 6.67kHz
Duty cycles: Set dc: -50.0%, Measured dc: -50.0%, period = 150.0us, f = 6.67kHz
Fixed duty tests complete
Duty cycles: Set dc: -23.0%, Measured dc: -23.0%, period = 150.0us, f = 6.67kHz
Duty cycles: Set dc: -41.0%, Measured dc: -41.0%, period = 150.0us, f = 6.67kHz
Duty cycles: Set dc: 30.0%, Measured dc: 30.0%, period = 150.0us, f = 6.67kHz
Duty cycles: Set dc: -50.0%, Measured dc: -50.0%, period = 150.0us, f = 6.67kHz
Random duty tests 1/2 complete
Duty cycles: Set dc: -50.0%, Measured dc: -50.0%, period = 150.0us, f = 6.67kHz
Resetting module...
Reset between duties complete
Duty cycles: Set dc: 25.0%, Measured dc: 25.0%, period = 150.0us, f = 6.67kHz
Duty cycles: Set dc: -41.0%, Measured dc: -41.0%, period = 150.0us, f = 6.67kHz
Duty cycles: Set dc: -58.0%, Measured dc: -58.0%, period = 150.0us, f = 6.67kHz
Random duty tests 2/2 complete
No errors in found!
*** ORDINARY TESTS DONE! ***
test sequencer passed
*****
** TEST STATUS SIM TIME (ns) REAL TIME (s) RATIO (ns/s) **
*****
** tb_pwm.fiat_sequencer FAIL 20.00 0.00 9572.14 **
** tb_pwm.test_sequencer PASS 3086089.38 8.07 382395.67 **
*****
** TESTS=2 PASS=1 FAIL=1 SKIP=0 3086109.38 8.14 379084.12 **
*****
<sys>:0: RuntimeWarning: coroutine 'FaultInjector.short_1' was never awaited
RuntimeWarning: Enable tracemalloc to get the object allocation traceback
<sys>:0: RuntimeWarning: coroutine 'FaultInjector.short_2' was never awaited
RuntimeWarning: Enable tracemalloc to get the object allocation traceback
<sys>:0: RuntimeWarning: coroutine 'FaultInjector.short_3' was never awaited

```

Explanation: What we can see here is that the testbench reports that we have messed up ordinary testing, because the injected faults did not cause ordinary testing to generate a report. If we did not have FIAT-tests, this would look like a test running without issues, unless we have other means to catch a test not run. A bad test would yield the same result.

If we remove the comments, to allow the reset check to run (line 131), while the short circuit still is disabled

```

async def run(self):
    ''' start all checks '''
    await Timer(1, 'ns') # Settle uninitialized values
    self.dut._log.info("Starting monitoring events")
    self.en_mon = SignalEventMonitor(self.dut.en)
    self.duty_mon = SignalEventMonitor(self.dut.duty_cycle)
    self.reset_mon = SignalEventMonitor(self.dut.reset)
    start_soon(self.check_reset())
    #start_soon(self.check_short_circuit())
    start_soon(self.check_timeout())
    start_soon(self.check_direction())
    start_soon(self.check_duty_cycle())

```

we will see that both the FIAT test and ordinary tests report errors.

```

0.00ns INFO cocotb.pulse_width_modulator *** FAULT INJECTION RUNNING ***
0.00ns INFO cocotb.pulse_width_modulator Resetting module...
../src/ieee2008/numeric_std-body.vhdl:3062:7:@0ms:(assertion warning): NUMERIC_STD.TO_INTEGER: metavalue detected, returning 0
0.00ns INFO cocotb.pulse_width_modulator Injecting error: Enable during reset...
1.00ns INFO cocotb.pulse_width_modulator Starting monitoring events
10.00ns INFO cocotb.pulse_width_modulator Completed: Reset test
20.00ns INFO cocotb.pulse_width_modulator Found error: Reset @ 10.0ns...
20.00ns INFO cocotb.pulse_width_modulator Injecting error: direction change during pulse...
20.00ns INFO cocotb.pulse_width_modulator Completed: Reset test
71.00ns INFO cocotb.pulse_width_modulator fiat_sequencer failed
71.00ns INFO cocotb.pulse_width_modulator Traceback (most recent call last):
File "/home/yngveha/Yngve/apptainer/usecase/test/tb_pwm.py", line 294, in fiat_sequencer
await fiat.run()
File "/home/yngveha/Yngve/apptainer/usecase/test/tb_pwm.py", line 338, in run
self.messages.find_error(self.dut, each[1])
File "/home/yngveha/Yngve/apptainer/usecase/test/tb_pwm.py", line 82, in find_error
raise AssertionError("NO_QUEUE")
AssertionError: NO_QUEUE
71.00ns INFO cocotb.pulse_width_modulator running test sequencer (2/2)
71.00ns INFO cocotb.pulse_width_modulator Starts monitoring tasks and stimuli generators
71.00ns INFO cocotb.pulse_width_modulator Starting clock
71.00ns INFO cocotb.pulse_width_modulator *** STARTING ORDINARY TESTS ***
71.00ns INFO cocotb.pulse_width_modulator Starting duty cycle tests
71.00ns INFO cocotb.pulse_width_modulator Resetting module...
72.00ns INFO cocotb.pulse_width_modulator Starting monitoring events
86.00ns INFO cocotb.pulse_width_modulator Completed: Reset test
250000.00ns INFO cocotb.pulse_width_modulator Duty cycles: Set dc: 50.0%, Measured dc: 50.0%, period = 150.0us, f = 6.67kHz
400000.00ns INFO cocotb.pulse_width_modulator Duty cycles: Set dc: 50.0%, Measured dc: 50.0%, period = 150.0us, f = 6.67kHz
700000.00ns INFO cocotb.pulse_width_modulator Duty cycles: Set dc: -50.0%, Measured dc: -50.0%, period = 150.0us, f = 6.67kHz
700000.00ns INFO cocotb.pulse_width_modulator Fixed duty tests complete
950781.25ns INFO cocotb.pulse_width_modulator Duty cycles: Set dc: 82.0%, Measured dc: 82.0%, period = 150.0us, f = 6.67kHz
1288281.25ns INFO cocotb.pulse_width_modulator Duty cycles: Set dc: -57.0%, Measured dc: -57.0%, period = 150.0us, f = 6.67kHz
1577734.38ns INFO cocotb.pulse_width_modulator Duty cycles: Set dc: 64.0%, Measured dc: 64.0%, period = 150.0us, f = 6.67kHz
1902343.75ns INFO cocotb.pulse_width_modulator Duty cycles: Set dc: 48.0%, Measured dc: 48.0%, period = 150.0us, f = 6.67kHz
1907343.75ns INFO cocotb.pulse_width_modulator Random duty tests 1/2 complete
2052343.75ns INFO cocotb.pulse_width_modulator Duty cycles: Set dc: 48.0%, Measured dc: 48.0%, period = 150.0us, f = 6.67kHz
2052343.75ns INFO cocotb.pulse_width_modulator Resetting module...
2052358.75ns INFO cocotb.pulse_width_modulator Reset between duties complete
2052358.75ns INFO cocotb.pulse_width_modulator Completed: Reset test
2357031.25ns INFO cocotb.pulse_width_modulator Duty cycles: Set dc: 45.0%, Measured dc: 45.0%, period = 150.0us, f = 6.67kHz
2659375.00ns INFO cocotb.pulse_width_modulator Duty cycles: Set dc: -43.0%, Measured dc: -43.0%, period = 150.0us, f = 6.67kHz
2995703.12ns INFO cocotb.pulse_width_modulator Duty cycles: Set dc: 19.0%, Measured dc: 19.0%, period = 150.0us, f = 6.67kHz
3047703.12ns INFO cocotb.pulse_width_modulator Random duty tests 2/2 complete
3047703.12ns INFO cocotb.pulse_width_modulator Error found: Reset @2052358.75ns
3047703.13ns INFO cocotb.pulse_width_modulator PWM enable has not been deasserted during reset
3047703.13ns INFO cocotb.pulse_width_modulator test_sequencer failed
3047703.13ns INFO cocotb.pulse_width_modulator Traceback (most recent call last):
File "/home/yngveha/Yngve/apptainer/usecase/test/tb_pwm.py", line 306, in test_sequence
messages.check_queue(dut)
File "/home/yngveha/Yngve/apptainer/usecase/test/tb_pwm.py", line 77, in check_queue
raise msg[2] # Provide traceback for the last error reported
File "/home/yngveha/Yngve/apptainer/usecase/test/tb_pwm.py", line 141, in check_reset
try: assert self.dut.en.value == 0, "PWM enable has not been deasserted during reset"
AssertionError: PWM enable has not been deasserted during reset
*****
** TEST STATUS SIM TIME (ns) REAL TIME (s) RATIO (ns/s) **
** tb_pwm.fiat_sequencer FAIL 71.00 0.00 19923.72 **
** tb_pwm.test_sequencer FAIL 3047632.12 7.99 381343.66 **
** TESTS=2 PASS=0 FAIL=2 SKIP=0 3047703.13 8.20 371825.78 **
*****

```

At this point, we have shown that we have a testbench created with FIAT-methodology, which will report when ordinary testing does not catch errors injected deliberately.

Not relevant to evaluation process, for interested readers:

The FIAT-tests has also been made with optional functionality to test reporting without modifying the ordinary tests. Changing the tests in the run method of the FaultInjector can be instructive if one simply want to test how reporting works, without turning off ordinary tests. By creating a mismatch between error type we search for and what is found we can trigger two sorts of error reports during FIAT-tests. That is either the report generated by ordinary failed tests, or the report that the FIAT-check did not find that specific error among the error reports.

By uncommenting line 324, or simply changing any test type to REPORT_ERROR we get the ordinary test output when injecting that fault.

By uncommenting (only) line 325 we will get to see the testbench output created when there are errors, but not the one we sought for. Line 325 runs the FIAT-reset test but asks for “not reported” (coloured green), which of course is not reported, and thus a FIAT-check error.

```
316 async def run(self):
317     ''' run all FIAT tests '''
318     self.dut._log.info("*** FAULT INJECTION RUNNING ***")
319
320     # To test ordinary reporting: change <fault>_TYPE to REPORT_ERROR in the List
321     # To test non-reported error, use "not reported" as error type
322     fiat_methods = [
323         (self.reset(), RESET_TYPE),
324         #(self.reset(), REPORT_ERROR), # uncomment for normal error report
325         #(self.reset(), "\x1b[1;32mnot_reported\x1b[0m"), # uncomment to test missing error report
326         (self.short_1(), SHORT_CIRCUIT_TYPE),
327         (self.short_2(), SHORT_CIRCUIT_TYPE),
328         (self.short_3(), SHORT_CIRCUIT_TYPE)
```

AE-checklist

- Algorithm: Are you presenting a new algorithm?
 - No, The methodology used has not been previously described in scientific papers we have found, but it is highly likely that engineers has used it sporadically in their work.
- Program: Which benchmarks do you use (PARSEC ARM real workloads, NAS, EEMBC, SPLASH, Rodinia, LINPACK, HPCG, MiBench, SPEC, cTuning, etc)? Are they included or should they be downloaded? Which version? Are they public or private? If they are private, is there a public analog to evaluate your artifact? What is the approximate size?
 - The testbenches used in this paper are all written by the author and can be shared freely.
- Compilation: Do you require a specific compiler? Public/private? Is it included? Which version?
 - VHDL and python compiler is required, all included in the aptainer image. See the installation section.
- Transformations: Do you require a program transformation tool (source-to-source, binary-to-binary, compiler pass, etc)? Public/private? Is it included? Which version?
 - No, all required software is included or described in the installation section.
- Binary: Are binaries included? OS-specific? Which version?
 - An aptainer .sif file is included, to create a simulation environment using only open-source tools. Descriptions are made for Linux or Windows subsystem for linux.
- Model: Do you use specific models (ImageNet, AlexNet, MobileNets)? Are they included? If not, how to download and install? What is their approximate size?
 - No.
- Data set: Do you use specific data sets? Are they included? If not, how to download and install? What is their approximate size?
 - All data required is generated by the author-created testbenches.
- Run-time environment: Is your artifact OS-specific (Linux, Windows, MacOS, Android, etc) ? Which version? Which are the main software dependencies (JIT, libs, run-time adaptation frameworks, etc); Do you need root access?
 - Linux OS root access is required to install the aptainer environment, and optionally a vcd waveform viewer. The aptainer.sif image runs Fedora linux, and does not require root access.
- Hardware: Do you need specific hardware (supercomputer, architecture simulator, CPU, GPU, neural network accelerator, FPGA) or specific features (hardware counters to measure power consumption, SUDO access to CPU/GPU frequency, etc)? Are they publicly available?
 - Any laptop running well known Linux distributions should be capable of running the tests. Aptainer can utilize GPU resources, but the open source software does not use these.
- Run-time state: Is your artifact sensitive to run-time state (cold/hot cache, network/cache contentions, etc.)
 - No
- Execution: Any specific conditions should be met during experiments (sole user, process pinning, profiling, adaptation, etc)? How long will it approximately run?
 - Each test should be able to run within 10-50 few seconds, depending on the hardware. Running through all the mentioned tests should take around 30 minutes.
- Metrics: Which metrics are reported (execution time, inference per second, Top1 accuracy, static and dynamic energy consumption, etc) - particularly important for multi-objective benchmarking, optimization and co-design (see ACM ReQuEST ML/SW/HW co-design tournaments).
 - The metrics for these tests are basically if each test has passed or not. The cocotb environment will report real time spent during testing, but this is not significant in this context.
- Output: What is your output (console, file, table, graph) and what is your result (exact output, numerical results, measured characteristics, etc)? Is expected result included?
 - The output is text reports to screen and waveforms in .vcd format

- Experiments: How to prepare experiments and replicate/reproduce results (OS scripts, manual steps by user, IPython/Jupyter notebook, automated workflows, etc)? Do not forget to mention the maximum allowable variation of empirical results!
 - See the [Evaluation Instructions](#) section.
- How much disk space required (approximately)?: This can help evaluators and end-users to find appropriate resources.
 - About 300MB, mostly for the `apptainer .sif` file
- How much time is needed to prepare workflow (approximately)?: This can help evaluators and end-users to estimate resources needed to evaluate your artifact.
 - Installation : about 10 minutes
- How much time is needed to complete experiments (approximately)?: This can help evaluators and end-users to estimate resources needed to evaluate your artifact.
 - Running the tests takes about 30-45 minutes.
- Publicly available?: Will your artifact be publicly available? If yes, we may spend an extra effort to help you with the documentation.
 - Yes!
- Code licenses (if publicly available)?: If your workflows and artifacts will be publicly available, please provide information about licenses. This will help the community to reuse your components.
 - All the software required is obtainable as open source
 - Fedora linux
 - MIT License
 - <https://docs.fedoraproject.org/en-US/legal/fedora-linux-license/>
 - GHDL 5.0.1, GTKwave
 - GNU GPLv2
 - <https://ghdl.github.io/ghdl/licenses.html>
 - <https://github.com/gtkwave/gtkwave?tab=GPL-2.0-1-ov-file>
 - Python 3.13
 - Python Software Foundation License version 2, Zero-Clause BSD License
 - <https://docs.python.org/3/license.html>
 - <https://docs.python.org/3/license.html#bsd0>
 - Numpy 2.2.4
 - NumPy license
 - <https://numpy.org/doc/2.2/license.html>
 - Cocotb 1.9.2
 - BSD 3-Clause "New" or "Revised" License
 - <https://github.com/cocotb/cocotb/blob/master/LICENSE>
 - *Git 2.49.0*
 - GPLv2
 - <https://opensource.org/license/GPL-2.0>
- Data licenses (if publicly available)?: If your workflows and artifacts will be publicly available, please provide information about licenses. This will help the community to reuse your components.
 - MIT License
- Workflow frameworks used?: Did authors use any workflow framework which can automate and customize experiments?
 - No
- Archived?: Note that the author-created artifacts relevant to this paper will receive the ACM "artifact available" badge *only if* they have been placed on a publicly accessible archival repository such as Zenodo, FigShare or Dryad. A DOI will be then assigned to their artifacts and must be provided here! Personal web pages, Google Drive, GitHub, GitLab and BitBucket are not accepted for this badge. Authors can provide this link at the end of the evaluation.
 - DOI: [10.5281/zenodo.15114023](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15114023)